

**A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON THE RESEARCH CONCEPTION OF
POSTGRADUATE STUDENTS IN THE LIBRARY SCHOOL AT TAI SOLARIN
UNIVERSITY OF EDUCATION AND UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN**

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Abstract

This study investigated the research conceptions of postgraduate students in the library schools at Tai Solarin University of Education and University of Ibadan. Three research questions were raised and two research hypotheses were formulated for this study. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. Research question one to three were tested using descriptive analysis techniques. Hypothesis one and two were tested with Pearson correlation coefficient. The findings revealed that postgraduates in the library school at University of Ibadan had a better conception of research ($\bar{x}=3.01$) in comparison to those in TASUED ($\bar{x}=2.75$) with their conception of research majorly focused on finding solution to problems ($\bar{x}=3.29$). The results of this study also indicated that while there is significant relationship between year of study and research conception of postgraduates in the library school at University of Ibadan ($r= 0.373$; $p < 0.05$), there was an inversely significant relationship between the year of study and research conception of postgraduates in the library school at TASUED ($r= -0.346$; $p < 0.05$). The study recommended among others that, seminars at various level of the

University (Faculty and departments) should be organised from time to time, with instructors cutting across those who have the cutting-edge skills in research as this will help to widen the scope of research conception beyond what it is at the moment.

Keywords: *Research conception, Postgraduates, Library school, TASUED, University of Ibadan.*

Introduction

A tertiary institution is known as an ivory tower which facilitate knowledge creation and sharing among the students. It is also a hub for academic and career development, which is achieved through the acquisition of degrees in their respective fields of interest. However, to achieve this, research activities need to be carried out. At the postgraduate level, emphasis is placed on research activities compared to the undergraduate level. The focus on research at the postgraduate level gives the students divergent views on what research means to influence how they approach research activities. The perception of research varies among postgraduates, academic staff, non-academic staff, and research consultants. Ellis and Stam (2015) also discussed how cross-cultural psychology reveals differences in cognition and research practices across various domains.

In a review of extant literature, there have been various conceptions of research by postgraduates. This conception has been of different shades depending on individual postgraduates under study. The study by Dennis, Li, Zhao, and Ross (2015) suggests that students' current understanding of research and its evolution is weak, despite their "positivist-like" understanding of research. They believe that research is primarily about experiments, control groups, numbers, and procedural elements associated with the scientific method.

Also, it can be opined that postgraduates in social sciences may not view research in the same way as those in the sciences and may have a lot to do with the importance of carrying out research for them. It may seem as though postgraduates in social sciences carry out research to fulfil the basic requirements of acquiring an academic qualification, and this could be their way of viewing research. This assertion is corroborated further by Lowrie, Morrison, Lees, Grant, Johnson, MacLean, Semple, Thomson, Harrison, Mullen, Lannigan, & Macdonald (2015), who inferred that the conception of research has to do with further education and acquisition of academic degrees rather than properly integrated into the heart of what is done as work.

Postgraduates may also conceptualise research within the context of their work. Anecdotally, research could connote evaluating the purpose of carrying out any activity and what can be learnt from it. Postgraduates with this conception believe in the expected outcome of research activities. For example, a student given a researchable topic to work on will seek to know the purpose of the topic and who will benefit from it. Relating this to research methods means the student has a basic understanding of the

objective of a study as well as the significance of a study, which could be termed a crucial aspect of research.

In another study, Dennis et al. (2017) concluded that despite the exposure of graduates to research activities as a course, they do not view themselves as having adequate skills that give them the advantage of becoming a part of the research community. They believe that they only do research as a course and not necessarily to have an understanding of research. This also meant that their conception of research is limited, and in such cases, they conceive research as being valid only when it is carried out within the university community.

Furthermore, several reasons can contribute to the varying conception of research by postgraduates. Among these factors are the research experiences of the postgraduates. McKie (2019) indicated that universities should enhance research value by managing students' research experiences, which influence their conception of research. It will foster critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability, essential in the job market. It could be inferred that a postgraduate in their first year of study may have a different research conception compared to a postgraduate in their advanced year. Consequently, based on the divergent conceptions of research by postgraduate students as influenced by their research experiences, this study seeks to investigate the conception of research among postgraduates in the library schools of two selected universities in southwest Nigeria.

Statement of the research problem

The increasing number of individuals pursuing higher education has led to a rise in postgraduate research activities, including assignments and dissertations. However, despite this growth, there is evidence of divergent views on research among postgraduates, often shaping their approach to research based on their personal conceptions. While prior studies have largely focused on academic staff and seasoned researchers, there is a notable gap in research examining the perspectives of postgraduate students, particularly Master's students in library schools. This study aims to address this gap by comparing the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library schools of Tai Solarin University of Education (TASUED) and the University of Ibadan.

A clear gap exists in exploring how Master's students in library schools perceive and approach research. The limited attention given to this group in the literature underscores the need for this comparative analysis, as their unique educational experiences and institutional contexts may influence their research conceptions in ways not yet fully understood. This study, therefore, seeks to contribute to the knowledge base by highlighting these differences and providing insights into the relationship between students' conceptions of research and their academic institutions.

Research questions

The following questions were raised to guide this study:

1. What are the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library school in tai solarin university of education?
2. What are the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library school in university of ibadan?
3. What is the comparison between the research conception of postgraduates in the library school in tai solarin university of education and university of education?

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated for this study is:

Ho1: There is no significant influence of the year of study on the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library school of Tai Solarin University of Education

Ho2: There is no significant influence of the year of study on the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library school of University of Ibadan.

Literature review

Kang & Yang (2022) conducted a study among English language teachers; conceptions of research ranged from seeing it as a “scientific endeavour” to more “practical applications tied to classroom innovation.” These varying conceptions underscore the importance of tailored research training that takes into account students' prior knowledge and academic culture. Daniel, Kumar, & Omar’s (2017) study of postgraduates revealed that postgraduate education participants view research as a significant body of knowledge, but there were differences in perceptions of what constitutes research and whether it should be considered a discipline. Some students view research as isolated facts without a deeper understanding. However, existing studies tend to focus on established scholars or doctoral students who engage in formal academic scholarship rather than undergraduates, at times Masters students, or whose primary relationship to inquiry will be from within non-academic personal and professional endeavours.

Lowrie et al. (2015) found that postgraduates gain research experience through academic qualifications, viewing it as a means to an end and a way to develop a better way of working to achieve a set objective. Dennis et al. (2017) investigated a study on graduate students at Indiana University. It was reported from the study that despite characterising research and inquiry as objective endeavours, some key distinctive features were also identified. Most of the graduate students differentiated between research conducted academically and daily life structure. Research was conceived as formal processes, while “inquiry” was conceived as processes of investigation carried out as a day-to-day activity. Research was also conceived as systematic, scientific, tedious, and a part of broader “inquiry processes that encompass all forms of investigation. This inferred that students’ conception of research as a formal and systematic effort is something that is far

from students' experiences. In a study by Hosein and Rao (2012), it was revealed that graduates who view research as finding out what currently exists in the literature and solutions to problems belong to the domino level. This connotes a low level of sophistication among the postgraduates.

Furthermore, the conception of research could be influenced by a lot of factors, which include research experience, work environment, and years of study. Peterson (2005) examined a study on medical students in Sweden. It was revealed that the students were at the end of the sixth semester in the third round of data collection. The majority of the students stated that the conception of research they had at the beginning of their studies had not changed despite spending 3 years in school. On the other hand, a minority of the students who had a low sophistication level of research conception at the beginning of their studies had now developed a more sophisticated conception of research based on the years of study. This implies that the student's year of study could influence their conception of research, while it also may not.

Consequently, it should be submitted that, based on the literature reviewed and considered for this study, it appears a lot of attention needs to be given to how postgraduates conceive research. Their conception of research will go a long way in determining their research approach, and as a result, it will affect their productivity. Postgraduates need to develop beyond the level of conceiving research as more than just another course of study required to be passed before academic certificates can be issued.

Methodology

A descriptive research design was used to guide this study. The design sought to compare the research conceptions of postgraduates in the library schools at Tai Solarin University of Education and the University of Ibadan. The population of this study is 65 master students of library schools in Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun, Ogun State, and 142 master students of the University of Ibadan.

For this study, the total enumeration technique was adopted to ensure the participation of all the postgraduates chosen in the study area. The total enumeration method results from the number of postgraduates involved. This is in line with Bryman (2006), who posits that using this technique occurs when respondents for the study are not too many. Therefore, the total number of postgraduates at the Master's level in library schools in the two selected universities as of the time of study was 207.

The measuring instrument used for this study is the questionnaire. "Research Conception of Postgraduates" was adapted from Meyer et al.'s (2005) Students' Conception in Research Inventory (SCoRI). To ensure the questionnaire's face validity, it was distributed to research experts in the Department of Library and Information Science. Thirty copies of the surveys were distributed to postgraduates at the University of Ilorin, Kwara State. The result shows a Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient for research

conception, $r = 0.98$. Thus, the measuring instrument is valid for the study based on the normality condition of $r \geq 0.70$.

The researchers personally handed out the questionnaire to the chosen participants at the library schools of both universities. From the 207 respondents, 176 (85.02%) copies of the questionnaire were duly completed and deemed usable for this study.

Results

Table 1: Presentation of demographic information of respondents in TASUED

Measure	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
School	TASUED	45	25.6
Age	18-25	11	24.4
	26-33	10	22.2
	34-41	21	46.7
	42-49	3	6.7
Gender	Male	21	46.7
	Female	24	53.3
Level of study	Masters 1	19	42.2
	Masters 2	26	57.8
Religion	Christianity	28	62.2
	Islam	17	37.8

Table 1 presents the demographic data collected at Tai Solarin University of Education. The result revealed that 21 (46.7%) respondents are within the age range of 34-41. The result further revealed that Masters 1 26 (57.8%) and Female 24 (53.3%) were the majority in terms of level of study and gender, respectively. Also, Christianity 28 (62.2%) forms the majority of the religion of postgraduates.

Table 2: Presentation of demographic information of respondents in University of Ibadan

Measure	Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)
School	University of Ibadan	131	74.4
Age	18-25	15	11.5
	26-33	61	46.6
	34-41	34	26.0
	42-49	21	16.0
Gender	Male	71	54.2
	Female	60	45.8
Level of study	Masters 1	62	47.3
	Masters 2	69	52.7
Religion	Christianity	75	57.3
	Islam	56	42.7

Table 2 presents the demographic information of respondents at the University of Ibadan. The result indicates that 61 (46.6%) respondents are within the age range of 26-33. The result further revealed that Masters 2 26 (52.7%) and Male 71 (54.2%) were the majority in terms of level of study and gender, respectively. Also, Christianity 75 (57.3%) forms the majority the religion of postgraduates in the research.

Table 3: Research conception of library school postgraduates in University of Ibadan

Misconceptions about research	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	SD
Good research specifically gathers data that will support the preconceived ideas	19 14.5%	9 6.9%	75 57.3%	28 21.4%	2.86	.9209
Research becomes true after it is published	10 7.6%	84 64.1%	9 6.9%	28 21.4%	2.42	.9111
If followed correctly research procedures will always yield positive results	19 14.5%	19 14.5%	56 42.7%	37 28.2%	2.85	.9959
When qualified people do research the results are always unbiased	19 14.5%	27 20.6%	66 50.4%	19 14.5%	2.65	.9023
Research is about collecting data which back your argument	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	73 55.7%	38 29.0%	3.06	.8204
It is quite acceptable to modify research data if it does not look exactly right	47 35.9%	27 20.6%	29 22.1%	28 21.4%	2.29	1.1668
If research is properly conducted, then contradictory research findings will never occur	19 14.5%	56 42.7%	37 28.2%	19 14.5%	2.43	.9117
Research means finding a definitive answer to specific questions	19 14.5%	19 14.5%	38 29.0%	55 42.0%	2.98	1.0740
Qualitative research is very biased compared with quantitative research	48 36.6%	65 49.5%	18 13.7%	-	1.77	.6744
The main purpose of research is to identify problems	20 15.3%	29 22.1%	46 35.1%	36 27.5%	2.75	1.0254
Research that is not scientific is not real research	19 14.5%	38 29.0%	37 28.2%	37 28.2%	2.70	1.0354
Mean					2.61	
Re-search						
Research is basically about comparison; new and previous results are compared	19 14.5%	10 7.6%	84 64.1%	18 13.7%	2.84	.7526
Research means finding out more information about something that is already there	-	10 7.6%	66 50.4%	55 42.0%	3.27	.8117

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Research is a systematic investigation to find out if there are facts that were left out by previous researchers	10 7.6%		75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886
Research is there to challenge research that has been done before	10 7.6%	28 21.4%	57 43.5%	36 27.5%	2.91	.8897
Research means information not considered in past research	10 7.6%	19 14.5%	57 43.5%	45 34.4%	3.05	.8932
Research is essentially about discovering something that already exists, but is hidden	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	66 50.4%	45 34.4%	3.11	.8471
Research means using findings to reinterpret what is already known	10 7.6%	9 6.9%	76 58.0%	36 27.5%	3.05	.8068
Research is the examination of old things in new ways rather than about discovering new things	9 6.9%	66 50.4%	47 35.9%	9 6.9%	2.43	.7236
Research is simply about unveiling what is already there	10 7.6%	46 35.1%	66 50.4%	9 6.9%	2.56	.7348
Research is always based on questions that are asked first	19 14.5%	46 35.1%	48 36.6%	18 13.7%	2.50	.9062
Doing research is the only way to develop theory	10 7.6%	9 6.9%	67 51.1%	45 34.4%	3.12	.8415
Mean					2.91	
Insightful process						
Sometimes when doing research, the pieces of information don't fit together and you need to study further and look for the pieces you need to complete the puzzle	10 7.6%		76 58.0%	45 34.4%	3.19	.7856
Research extends current concepts to obtain a better understanding	10 7.6%		75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886
Research provides a deeper insight and understanding of a particular topic	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	75 57.3%	36 27.5%	3.05	.8121
Research stimulates further interest or work in the area	10 7.6%	-	85 64.9%	36 27.5%	3.12	.7547
Even the newest ideas germinate in a fertile bed of previous knowledge and ideas	10 7.6%	-	75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886
Research means searching for more knowledge in a particular field; to accumulate more knowledge	10	-	66 50.4%	55 42.0%	3.34	.6173
Research summarizes existing knowledge and/or new knowledge to	10 7.6%		75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886

create previously unknown insights						
Research is defined as a mechanism to add more knowledge to existing knowledge	10 7.6%	-	75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886
Ongoing research raises new questions and thus creates new research	10 7.6%		66 50.4%	55 42.0%	3.27	.8117
Research means studying a particular subject of interest in depth	10 7.6%	18 13.7%	48 36.6%	55 42.0%	3.13	.9232
The understanding of researched phenomena is the basis for new technologies	10 7.6%	19 14.5%	46 35.1%	56 42.7%	3.13	.9315
Research is something you do when you want to find information	10 7.6%	- 56.5%	74 35.9%	47 35.9%	3.21	.7915
There is no beginning or ending to research; there is always something new to study	10 7.6%	18 13.7%	38 29.0%	65 49.6%	3.21	.9505
Mean					3.19	
Finding solutions to problems,						
Research is fundamentally about finding the truth	20 15.3%	9 6.9%	37 28.2%	65 49.6%	3.12	1.0815
Basically research is concerned with uncovering the truth	10 7.6%	19 14.5%	37 28.2%	65 49.6%	3.20	.9561
Research means a systematic hunting for truths about a subject	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	37 28.2%	74 56.5%	3.36	.9166
Research is done in order to determine the truth or validity about something	10 7.6%	-	38 29.0%	83 63.4%	3.48	.8445
Mean					3.29	
Discovering the truth						
Research is about finding solutions to problems	10 7.6%	-	56 42.7%	65 49.6%	3.34	.8299
Research means collecting data to solve particular problems	10 7.6%	0 0%	84 64.1%	37 28.2%	3.27	.8117
Research is basically a tool for answering questions	10 7.6%	0 0%	84 64.1%	37 28.2%	3.13	.7585
Research is the careful and thorough study of a problem	10 7.6%	0 0%	75 57.3%	46 35.1%	3.20	.7886
Research means investigating and trying to prove whether a new idea is correct	10 7.6%	9 6.9%	75 57.3%	37 28.2%	3.06	.8110
Research means finding out specific	19	27	39	46	2.86	1.0606

information about an unknown subject	14.5%	20.6%	29.8	35.1%		
Research means discovering something which was not known before	10 7.6%	18 13.7%	57 43.5%	46 35.1%	3.06	.8923
Research always begins with a question	10 7.6%	19 14.5%	37 28.2%	65 49.6%	3.20	.9561
Mean					3.14	
Gathering information.						
Researching a particular topic can never be complete	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	74 56.5%	37 28.2%	3.05	.8163
The information, techniques, and perspectives which flow from research affect the way in which problems are perceived	10 7.6%	10 7.6%	65 49.6%	46 35.1%	3.12	.8506
Qualified people do not need permission to do research	9 6.9%	57 43.5%	37 28.2%	28 21.2%	2.64	.8950
Mean					2.94	

Key: Strongly Disagree = SD; Disagree = D; Agree = A; Strongly Agree = SA
Criterion mean (\bar{x} = 2.50) Weighted Mean (\bar{x} = 3.01)

The result (Table 3) showed that the respondents indicated that it is quite acceptable to modify research data if it does not look exactly right (\bar{x} = 3.06; SD = .8204); research means finding a definitive answer to specific questions (\bar{x} = 2.98; SD = 1.0740); good research specifically gathers data that will support the preconceived ideas (\bar{x} = 2.86; SD = .9209); if research is properly conducted (\bar{x} = 2.29; SD = 1.1668); and qualitative research is very biased compared with quantitative research (\bar{x} = 1.77; SD = .6744).

The result further revealed that research means to accumulate more knowledge (\bar{x} = 3.34; SD = .6173); ongoing research raises new questions and thus creates new research (\bar{x} = 3.27; SD = .8117); research is something you do when you want to find information (\bar{x} = 3.21; SD = .7915); there is no beginning or ending to research; there is always something new to study (\bar{x} = 3.21; SD = .9505); research is the examination of old things in new ways rather than about discovering new things (\bar{x} = 2.43; SD = .7236).

It was a remarkable find that research means systematic hunting for truths about a subject (\bar{x} = 3.36; SD = .9166); research is carried out to determine the truth or validity about something (\bar{x} = 3.48; SD = .8445); research is about finding solutions to problems (\bar{x} = 3.34; SD = .8299); and qualified people do not need permission to do research (\bar{x} = 2.64; SD = .8950).

Table 3 revealed the research conception of University of Ibadan postgraduates. The table revealed variations in the weighted mean of each component of the research

conception. These components measuring the responses of the postgraduates showed their conception of research as a misconception about research (\bar{x} = 2.61); re-search (\bar{x} = 2.91); insightful process (\bar{x} = 3.19); finding solutions to problems (\bar{x} = 3.29); discovering the truth (\bar{x} = 3.14); gathering information (\bar{x} = 2.94). Inferentially, postgraduates in the University of Ibadan library school view research more as “finding solutions to problems.”.

Table 4: Research conception of library school postgraduates in Tai Solarin University of Education.

Misconceptions about research	SD	D	A	SA	\bar{x}	SD
Good research specifically gathers data that will support the preconceived ideas	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	20 44.4%	5 11.1%	2.56	.8409
Research becomes true after it is published	-	35 77.8%	10 22.2%	-	2.22	.4204
If followed correctly research procedures will always yield positive results	10 22.2%	15 33.3%	-	20 44.4%	2.67	1.2613
When qualified people do research the results are always unbiased	10 22.2%	15 33.3%	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	2.56	1.1785
Research is about collecting data which back your argument	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	20 44.4%	3.00	1.0660
It is quite acceptable to modify research data if it does not look exactly right	10 22.2%	10 22.5%	20 44.4%	5 11.1%	2.44	.9666
If research is properly conducted, then contradictory research findings will never occur	10 22.2%	5 11.1%	30 66.7%	-	2.44	.8409
Research means finding a definitive answer to specific questions	10 22.2%	-	25 55.6%	10 22.2%	2.78	1.0421
Qualitative research is very biased compared with quantitative research	-	15 33.3%	30 66.7%	-	2.67	.4767
The main purpose of research is to identify problems	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	30 66.7%	-	2.56	.6297
Research that is not scientific is not real research	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	30 66.7%	-	2.56	.6927
Mean					2.59	
Re-search						
Research is basically about comparison; new and previous results are compared	5 11.1%	-	20 44.4%	20 44.4%	3.22	.9266

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Research means finding out more information about something that is already there	5 11.1%	-	35 77.8%	5 11.1%	2.89	.7454
Research is a systematic investigation to find out if there are facts that were left out by previous researchers	5 11.1%	-	30 66.7%	10 22.2%	3.00	.8257
Research is there to challenge research that has been done before	5 11.1%	-	40 88.9%	-	2.78	.6356
Research means information not considered in past research	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	15 33.3%	15 33.3%	2.89	1.0054
Research is essentially about discovering something that already exists, but is hidden	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	20 44.4%	15 33.3%	3.00	.9535
Research means using findings to reinterpret what is already known	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	20 44.4%	3.11	1.0050
Research is the examination of old things in new ways rather than about discovering new things	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	35 77.8%	-	2.67	.6742
Research is simply about unveiling what is already there	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	20 44.4%	3.11	1.0050
Research is always based on questions that are asked first	5 11.1%	-	30 66.7%	10 22.2%	3.00	.8257
Doing research is the only way to develop theory	5 11.1%	-	25 55.6%	15 33.3%	3.11	.8848
Mean					2.98	
Insightful process						
Sometimes when doing research, the pieces of information don't fit together and you need to study further and look for the pieces you need to complete the puzzle	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	20 44.4%	15 33.3%	3.00	.9535
Research extends current concepts to obtain a better understanding	10 22.2%	-	15 33.3%	20 44.4%	3.00	1.1678
Research provides a deeper insight and understanding of a particular topic	5 11.1%	-	20 44.4%	20 44.4%	3.22	.9266
Research stimulates further interest or work in the area	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	25 55.6%	3.22	1.0421
Even the newest ideas germinate in a fertile bed of previous knowledge and ideas	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	35 77.8%	-	2.67	.6742
Research means searching for	10	-	15	20	3.00	1.1678

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more knowledge in a particular field; to accumulate more knowledge	22.2%		33.3%	44.4%		
Research summarizes existing knowledge and/or new knowledge to create previously unknown insights	5 11.1%	-	30 66.7%	10 22.2%	3.00	.82572
Research is defined as a mechanism to add more knowledge to existing knowledge	5 11.1%	-	20 44.4%	20 44.4%	3.22	.9266
Ongoing research raises new questions and thus creates new research	15 33.3%	-	25 55.6%	5 11.1%	2.44	1.0778
Research means studying a particular subject of interest in depth	5 11.1%	-	40 88.9%	-	2.78	.6356
The understanding of researched phenomena is the basis for new technologies	5 11.1%	-	35 77.8%	5 11.1%	2.89	.7454
Research is something you do when you want to find information	15 33.3%	-	15 33.3%	15 33.3%	2.67	1.2613
There is no beginning or ending to research; there is always something new to study	5 11.1%	10 33.3%	10 33.3%	20 44.4%	3.00	1.0660
Mean					2.93	
Finding solutions to problem						
Research is fundamentally about finding the truth	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	15 33.3%	15 33.3%	2.89	1.0050
Basically research is concerned with uncovering the truth	10 22.2%	5 11.1%	10 22.2%	20 44.4%	2.89	1.2102
Research means a systematic hunting for truths about a subject	5 11.1%	5 11.1%	25 55.6%	10 22.6%	2.89	.8848
Research is done in order to determine the truth or validity about something	10 22.2%	-	20 44.4%	15 33.3%	2.89	1.1124
Mean					2.89	
Discovering the truth						
Research is about finding solutions to problems	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	15 33.3%	10 22.2%	2.66	.9535
Research means collecting data to solve particular problems	15 33.3%	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	2.33	1.1678
Research is basically a tool for answering questions	15 33.3%	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	10 22.2%	2.44	1.1785

Research is the careful and thorough study of a problem	5 11.1%	20 44.4%	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	2.56	.9666
Research means investigating and trying to prove whether a new idea is correct	-	10 22.2%	20 44.4%	15 33.3%	3.11	.7454
Research means finding out specific information about an unknown subject	-	10 22.2%	25 55.6%	10 22.2%	3.00	.6742
Research means discovering something which was not known before	-	20 44.4%	10 22.5%	15 33.3%	2.89	.8848
Research always begins with a question	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	10 22.2%	15 33.3%	2.67	1.1678
Mean					2.71	
Gathering information						
Researching a particular topic can never be complete	20	5 11.1%	15 33.3%	5 11.1%	2.11	1.1124
The information, techniques, and perspectives which flow from research affect the way in which problems are perceived	5 11.1%	20 44.4%	15 33.3%	5 11.1%	2.44	.8409
Qualified people do not need permission to do research	10 22.2%	5 11.1%	25 55.6%	5 22.2%	2.56	.9666
Mean					2.37	

Key: Strongly Disagree = SD; Disagree = D; Agree = A; Strongly Agree = SA
Criterion mean (\bar{x} = 2.50) Weighted Mean (\bar{x} = 2.75)

The result (Table 4) showed that the respondents indicated that it is quite acceptable to modify research data if it does not look exactly right (\bar{x} = 3.00; SD = 1.0660); research means finding a definitive answer to specific questions (\bar{x} = 2.78; SD = 1.0421); qualitative research is very biased compared with quantitative research (\bar{x} = 2.67; SD = .4767); research becomes true after it is published, if followed correctly research procedures will always yield positive results (\bar{x} = 2.22; SD = .4204).

The result further revealed that research is basically about comparison; new and previous results are compared (\bar{x} = 3.22; SD = .9266); research provides a deeper insight and understanding of a particular topic (\bar{x} = 3.22; SD = .9266); research stimulates further interest or work in the area (\bar{x} = 3.22; SD = 1.0421); and research is defined as a mechanism to add more knowledge to existing knowledge (\bar{x} = 3.22; SD = .9266).

It was also revealed that research means investigating and trying to prove whether a new idea is correct (\bar{x} = 3.11; SD = .7454); research means finding out specific information about an unknown subject (\bar{x} = 3.00; SD = .6742); research means collecting data to solve

particular problems (=2.33; SD=1.1678); and researching a particular topic can never be complete (=2.11; SD=1.1124).

Table 4 revealed variations in the weighted mean of each component of research conception. These components measuring the responses of the postgraduates showed their conception of research as: misconception about research (\bar{x} =2.59); re-search (\bar{x} = 2.98); insightful process (\bar{x} = 2.93); finding solutions to problem (\bar{x} =2.89); discovering the truth (\bar{x} =2.71); gathering information (\bar{x} =2.37). Inferentially, postgraduates in TASUED library school view research more as a “re- search”.

Table 5: Comparison of the research conception of TASUED library school’s postgraduates and the research conception of University of Ibadan library school’s postgraduates

S/N	Research conception (components)	TASUED (\bar{x})	University of Ibadan (\bar{x})
1.	Misconception about research	2.59	2.61
2.	Re-search	2.98	2.91
3.	Insightful process	2.93	3.19
4.	Finding solution to problems	2.89	3.29
5.	Discovering the truth	2.71	3.14
6.	Gathering information	2.37	2.94
	Weighted mean	2.75	3.01

Table 5 revealed that the conception of research by postgraduates of both library schools on “misconception about research” appears significant, although the library school postgraduates in University of Ibadan have a better perspective of the “misconceptions about research” with a mean score of (=2.61) than their colleagues from Tai Solarin University of Education. The postgraduates in TASUED library school have a better conception of research on “re-search” (= 2.98) when compared with the conception of research by University of Ibadan library school postgraduates (= 2.91). The results from table 5 further revealed that University of Ibadan had a better view of the other components of research conception; insightful process (=3.19); finding solutions to problem (=3.29); discovering the truth (=3.14); gathering information (=2.94) when compared with that of TASUED library school postgraduates; insightful process (=2.93); finding solutions to problem (=2.89); discovering the truth (=2.71); gathering information (=2.37). Furthermore, the overall mean of the conceptions on research by postgraduates revealed that University of Ibadan library school postgraduates have a better research conception (=3.01) in comparison to TASUED’s library school postgraduates (=2.75).

Table 6: Relationship between year of study and research conception of library school postgraduates in Tai Solarin University of Education.

Correlations			
		Research Conception	Level of respondents
Research Conception	Pearson Correlation	1	-.346*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.020
	N	45	45
Level of respondents	Pearson Correlation	-.346*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.020	
	N	45	45

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 6 shows the correlation coefficient for the relationship between the year of study and research conception of postgraduates at the library school of Tai Solarin University of Education. The result revealed that the coefficient is ($r = -0.346$; $p < 0.05$), and the relationship is negative. The result shows an inversely significant relationship between the year of study and the research conception of postgraduates at the library school of Tai Solarin University of Education; hence, the hypothesis is rejected. It is possible to infer that postgraduate students' conceptions of research will decline with an increase in study year, although only for 34.6% of respondents.

Table 7: Relationship between year of study and research conception of library school postgraduates in University of Ibadan

Correlations			
		Research Conception	Level of respondents
Research Conception	Pearson Correlation	1	.373**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	131	131
Level of respondents	Pearson Correlation	.373**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	131	131

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 7 shows the correlation coefficient for the relationship between the year of study and research conception of postgraduates at the library school at the University of Ibadan. The result revealed that the coefficient is ($r = 0.373$; $p < 0.05$) and that the relationship is positive. The result shows a significant relationship between the year of study and the research conception of postgraduates at the library school at the University of Ibadan; hence, the hypothesis is rejected. The year of study for postgraduates at the University of Ibadan will influence their conception of research.

Discussion of findings

The findings of this study revealed that library school postgraduates at the University of Ibadan have a better conception of research than library school postgraduates at TASUED. Among the dominant conceptions of research between the two library schools is the view of research as a means of "finding solutions to problems." Postgraduates viewed research as a systematic way to discover the truth about any subject.

Per the findings of this study, Dennis et al. (2017) reported the view of graduate students of Indiana University that the conceived research is systematic, scientific, tedious, and a part of broader "inquiry processes that encompass all forms of investigation. This inferred that it is agreed that students' conception of research is a formal and systematic effort geared towards problem-solving. This finding is further corroborated by the independent submission of one of the respondents, who opined that "research is the process of finding solutions to an identified problem." To further corroborate the study, Brew (2000) described researchers as being at a "domino conception" level (a focus on solving problems or answering questions), which is directly related to the conception of research as "finding solutions to problems". However, Hosein and Rao (2012) disagreed with the findings of this study, as it was reported that graduates who view research as finding out what currently exists in the literature and solutions to problems belong to the domino level. This connotes a low level of sophistication among the postgraduates. This might be related to the influence of the university's curriculum and teaching methods.

The study's findings also revealed that research was thought of as "re-search," particularly by postgraduates in the library school at Tai Solarin University of Education. The respondents further viewed that research is basically about new and previous comparisons of results. This finding is further validated by one of the participants of this study, who viewed research as a synthesis of various viewpoints leading to a new idea. The results of this investigation revealed an inversely significant relationship between the year of study and the research conception of postgraduates at TASUED's library school. However, there is a relationship between the year of study and research conception among postgraduates at the University of Ibadan's library school. Peterson's (2005) study on Swedish medical students "provides support for" this finding. It found that the students in the third round of data collection were nearing the end of their sixth semester. A majority of the students stated that the conception of research they had at the beginning of their studies had not changed despite spending 3 years in school. On the other hand, a minority of the students who possessed a low sophistication level of research conception at the beginning of their studies had now developed a more sophisticated conception of research based on the years of study.

It could also be inferred that postgraduates in the first year may not have sufficient knowledge of areas of interest in research as they have not covered aspects of the curriculum that will help improve their conception of research. Postgraduate students

who have completed more than two semesters may have the necessary experience to develop research topics and titles, as well as a deeper understanding of research.

Conclusion

Postgraduates' approach to research is determined by how they conceive it; hence, this study attempted to examine the research conception of postgraduates in the library schools at TASUED and the University of Ibadan. This study also compared the research conception of postgraduates of the library school in TASUED and the University of Ibadan. "It was an astonishing discovery that postgraduates in the library school at the University of Ibadan have a better conception of research than their counterparts from TASUED. This could be connected to the significant relationship between the year of study and research conception of the postgraduates in the library school at the University of Ibadan. However, it was reported that the year of study and research conception of postgraduates in the library school at TASUED did not have a significant relationship. Thus, it never affected their research view. By comparing postgraduates' research conceptions at Tai Solarin University of Education (TASUED) and the University of Ibadan, the study highlights the disparity in research approaches between students at the two universities. It identifies a strong relationship between the year of study and research conception at the University of Ibadan, suggesting that more experienced students develop a deeper understanding of research. This insight can help inform curriculum design and research training programs.

Recommendation

Based on the outcome of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The University management should put in place policies that will facilitate postgraduate students' continuous exposure to current research activities all through their duration of study.
2. The postgraduate college should expose their postgraduate students to continuous research trainings beyond departmental courses on research methods. Seminars at various level of the University (Faculty and departments) should be organised from time to time with instructors cutting across those who have the cutting-edge skills in research. This will help to widen the scope of research conception beyond what it is at the moment.
3. Postgraduates should be encouraged to collaborate more with researchers on academic social media sites such as LinkedIn, ResearchGate and Google Scholar.

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